

**DYNAMIC DIELECTRIC ANALYSIS
FOR NONDESTRUCTIVE CURE
MONITORING AND PROCESS CONTROL**

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ABSTRACT

Dynamic dielectric analysis (DDA) is an instrumental means for quantitative material evaluation and closed loop "smart" cure cycle control. DDA is particularly important to process control because it is one of only a few experimental techniques for conveniently studying the cure process continuously, that is, to examine the cure chemistry throughout the process of going from a monomeric liquid of varying viscosity to a crosslinked, insoluble, high temperature solid [1-3]. The key for achieving this goal is to relate the chemistry of the cure process to the dielectric properties of the polymer system by correlating time, temperature and frequency dependent dielectric measurements with other chemical characterization methods.

The frequency dependence of the DDA measurement of ϵ^* is used to isolate and characterize ionic translational diffusion and dipolar rotational diffusion. This molecular information provides a means for monitoring the course of the reaction and the viscosity. From the frequency dependence of the dielectric loss, a specific conductivity is calculated which, in turn, is related to viscosity and extent of reaction.

Dielectric characterization measurements have been made on aromatic polyimide, epoxy, and thermoplastic resin systems. DDA is used to monitor reaction progress, the effect of age and moisture, and thermoplastic phase changes. It is also shown to be an effective in-situ method for monitoring viscosity, and relative degree of cure within a thick laminate.

INTRODUCTION

A nondestructive in-situ electromagnetic-dielectric impedance measurement technique has been developed for sensing (both in a research and production tool) the cure processing properties of high-temperature, high-performance thermoplastics and thermosets [1-5]. The technique emphasizes continuous frequency dependent dielectric measurement and analysis throughout the cure cycle. The instrumentation can measure the

complex permittivity, an intrinsic polymer property, over 9 orders of magnitude (10^{-3} to 10^6) and 6 decades of frequency (Hz to MHz) at temperatures to 400°C . The frequency dependence of the complex permittivity is used in conjunction with dielectric theory to determine molecular parameters which monitor the ionic and dipolar diffusion processes. These parameters serve as molecular probes of the chemical and physical changes occurring during cure. The Hz to MHz electromagnetic frequency range is advantageous as it senses both ionic and dipolar diffusion processes and minimizes extraneous sensing problems.

In this report electromagnetic sensing is used to measure and monitor processing properties in both high performance thermoplastics and thermosets. Using as examples PEEK, a semicrystalline thermoplastic, and two TGDDM-amine based epoxies we show that electromagnetic sensing can be used to monitor the viscosity, T_g , crystal melting, recrystallization, residual solvent content and evolution, and extent of reaction. These processing properties can be used to help define an optimal processing window and to determine the actual state of the polymer as a function of position, time and temperature in a production tool.

The major objective of this work is the development of frequency dependent electromagnetic techniques as a smart sensor for quantitative nondestructive material evaluation and intelligent closed loop process control in laboratory and processing environments.

EXPERIMENTAL

Frequency dependent electromagnetic-dynamic dielectric measurements were made using a Hewlett-Packard 4192A LF Impedance Analyzer controlled by a 9836 Hewlett-Packard computer. Measurements at frequencies from 5 to 5×10^6 Hz were taken at regular intervals during the cure cycle and converted to the complex permittivity, $\epsilon^* = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''$. Measurements were made with a geometry independent Dek Dyne DDA Sensor.* A detailed description of the procedure has been given elsewhere [5].

Viscosity measurements were done using a Rheometrics System IV-dynamic mechanical spectrometer.

DSC measurements were made using a Perkin-Elmer DSC-7 differential scanning calorimeter.

The PEEK and TGDDM epoxy samples were furnished by NASA-Langley and used as received.

THEORY

Frequency dependent measurements of the complex impedance, characterized by C and G, were used to calculate the complex permittivity $\epsilon^* = \epsilon' - i\epsilon''$. This calculation is possible when using a probe whose geometry is invariant over all measurement conditions.*

Both the real and the imaginary parts of ϵ^* can have a dipolar and an ionic component [6]. The dipolar component arises from diffusion of bound charge or molecular dipole moments. The frequency dependence of the polar component may be represented by the Cole-Davidson function in which τ is a characteristic relaxation time and β is a parameter which measures the distribution in relaxation times. The dipolar term is generally the major component of the dielectric signal at high frequencies and in highly viscous media.

The ionic component, ϵ_i^* , often dominates ϵ^* at low frequencies, low viscosities and/or higher temperatures. The presence of mobile ions gives rise to localized layers of charge near the electrodes. Since these space charge layers are separated by very small molecular distances on the order of \AA^0 , the corresponding space charge capacitance can become extremely large, with ϵ' on the order of 10^6 . Johnson and Cole, while studying formic acid, derived empirical equations for the ionic contribution to ϵ^* in terms of σ , the conductivity ($\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), an intensive variable, in contrast to conductance $G(\text{ohm}^{-1})$ which is dependent upon cell and sample size [7]. Their equations show that electrode polarization makes dielectric measurements increasingly difficult to interpret and use as the frequency of measurement becomes lower.

Analysis of the frequency dependence of $\epsilon^*(\omega)$ in the Hz to MHz range is, in general, optimum for determining both σ and τ . In turn, the ionic parameter, σ and the dipolar parameter, τ are directly related on a molecular level to the rate of ionic translational diffusion and dipolar rotational mobility [6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PEEK

First we examine the capability of frequency dependent electromagnetic sensing to detect the glass, amorphous, crystalline and melt phase transitions of a high performance thermoplastic. The poly (aryl-ether-ether-ketone) thermoplastic PEEK in its semi-crystalline

state was heated to 360° , held 30 minutes and then cooled. The $\epsilon'' \times 2\pi$ frequency data taken in a press are shown in Fig. 1. The electromagnetic sensor is able to detect T_g at 145° , melting at 342° , recrystallization of the supercooled melt at 295° and the cooling glass transition at 145° . These phase changes have been confirmed by DSC.

A plot of $\epsilon'' \times 2\pi$ frequency shows visually the dipolar and ionic contributions to the loss term. When the $\epsilon'' \times 2\pi$ frequency curves differ at each frequency, the molecular processes contributing to ϵ'' are bound charge dipole-like diffusion processes. Overlapping curves indicate translational diffusion of charged species is the dominant molecular process determining the loss ϵ'' .

Below the glass transition, the rate of translational diffusion of ions is extremely slow and the value of the loss ϵ'' is small. A frequency-dependent dipole-like relaxation can be observed just above T_g . The maximum in ϵ'' at a given frequency corresponds to the relaxation rate, τ , of the dipolar rotational diffusion process. At the temperature of the $\epsilon''(f)$ maximum, $\tau(T) = 1/(2\pi f)$. As the temperature increases, the polymer becomes more fluid so that the dipoles can orient faster. Thus ϵ'' max for the higher frequencies occurs at the higher temperatures. As the temperature increases, ionic translation contributes to the loss at increasingly higher frequencies.

Shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 are the values of ϵ' and $\epsilon'' \times 2\pi f$ at 5 kHz for an amorphous PEEK sample (less than 2% crystalline (8)) on heat up to 220° , a hold at 220° and cool down. The value of ϵ' senses at 166° a cool crystallization process and the accompanying polarization changes which occur over molecular dimensions as the polymer crystallizes. The onset of the cool crystallization process just above T_g at 160° is verified by DSC. The capability of the frequency dependent electromagnetic-sensing to characterize the glass, amorphous, crystalline, states as well as phase changes of the polymer through quantitative measurement of τ , σ and ϵ^* is possible. The advantage of the technique is not only that the measurement can be made in-situ in a production tool but that sensitivity is not affected by use of a slow annealing process.

TGDDM Epoxy

The frequency dependence of the real and the imaginary parts of the

complex permittivity are used to determine σ and τ , the ionic and dipolar contributions to ϵ^* . These parameters are measured during cure as a function of time and in turn related to degree of cure for four isothermal cures. The dependence of σ and τ on degree of cure, α , is shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. As expected, for similar degrees of advancement of the reaction α , the ionic mobility as measured by σ increases with temperature. Similarly the dipolar mobility increases with temperature. An increase in dipolar mobility corresponds to shorter relaxation times. Thus τ decreases as temperature increases.

The rate of change of $\log \sigma$ with time and α drops by several orders of magnitude once the advancement of the reaction approaches the point where $T_g = T_{\text{cure}}$. The point at which $\frac{d\sigma}{dt}$ and $\frac{d\sigma}{d\alpha}$ drops sharply is T_g . The values of α at this point, .72 at 165°, .80 at 180°, and .88 at 195° are in good agreement with our α_{T_g} values determined by DSC scans.

The correlation during cure of $-\log \sigma$ with $\log \eta$ (viscosity) and the ability to use frequency dependent $\epsilon^*(\omega)$ measurements to determine σ , thereby accurately detecting points of maximum flow during cure, was first shown by us several years ago [1,2]. The qualitative correlation of $-\log \sigma$ and $\log \eta$ is clearly demonstrated in Fig. 6. The quantitative relationship of $\log \sigma$ and $\log \eta$ is shown for two isothermal cures in Fig. 7. To a first approximation one might look for a plot of $\log (\sigma)$ vs $\log (\eta)$ to be linear. Fig. 7 shows that there is a break in the $\sigma \eta$ dependence as the resin approaches a viscosity of 10^3 poise, a value associated with gel.

The relation of $\log \tau$ to $\log \eta$ is shown in Fig. 8. The relationship is indeed approximately linear. This apparent linear dependence is due in part to the smaller range of η and that the measurements of τ are made before η reaches 10^3 poise or gel.

Finally, we show the results of an application of this type of analysis to measure ϵ^* and thereby σ and viscosity during cure as a function of position in a thick laminate. The data were taken on a 192 ply TGDDM epoxy graphite laminate during cure in a 4 by 18 foot production size autoclave.

A series of runs measured simultaneously the viscosity and the value of $\epsilon^*(\omega)$ for temperature ramp-hold sequences similar to those observed in the autoclave cure. Using the frequency dependence of ϵ^* , the value of σ , reflecting ionic diffusion was determined and correlated with viscosity. The results of these correlation studies were used to

quantitatively relate σ to viscosity.

Shown in Fig. 9, is the resin viscosity measured at the four ply locations inside the 192 ply composite determined from the ionic mobility parameter σ . The measured values of the viscosity determined by $\epsilon^*(\omega)$ show significant differences for different ply position for both the time of maximum flow and the value of the viscosity minima. Time differences of up to 20 minutes between the center and surface ply are measured. The viscosity minima is observed to be lower for the surface ply than the center ply in the low temperature hold but higher for the surface ply in the high temperature hold. The measured values of the viscosity at each ply are in good agreement with the predicted values of the viscosity using the Loos-Springer cure process model [9,10].

CONCLUSIONS

Frequency dependent electromagnetic sensing of ϵ^* in the Hz to MHz vision and determination of molecular parameters σ and τ describing the diffusion rates of ions and dipoles is a sensing technique which can be used to characterize the solvent, glass, amorphous, and crystalline state of thermoplastics as well as phase changes therein. Similarly $\epsilon^*(\omega)$, σ and τ can be used to measure the viscosity and degree of cure in thermosets. The advantage of the technique is that the measurement can be made in-situ in a production tool both in the laboratory and during production.

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*Inquiries regarding the Dek Dyne sensor probe and the DDA instrumentation should be directed to D. Kranbuehl.

The dielectric work was made possible in part through the support of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration-Langley Research Center research grant No. NAG 1-237.

Figure 1. Semicrystalline PEEK: $\epsilon'' \times 2\pi f$ vs. time.

Figure 2. Amorphous PEEK: ϵ' vs. temperature (5kHz)

Figure 3. Amorphous PEEK: ϵ'' vs. temperature (5kHz)

Figure 4. TGDDM Epoxy: Ionic mobility, σ , vs. degree of cure, α .

Figure 5. TGDDM Epoxy: Relaxation time, τ , vs. degree of cure, α .

Figure 6. TGDDM Epoxy: Simultaneous measurement of ionic mobility and viscosity.

Figure 7. TGDDM Epoxy: Ionic mobility, σ , vs. viscosity, η .

Figure 8. TGDDM Epoxy: Relaxation time, τ , vs. viscosity, η .

Figure 9. 192 ply TGDDM Epoxy Graphite Laminate: Resin viscosity determined from the frequency dependence of ϵ^* .